

SHORT NOTES

MERCAPTAN AS A CHAIN-TRANSFER AGENT IN EMULSION POLYMERISATION OF STYRENE

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Although mercaptan is being used in emulsion polymerisation of butadiene-styrene on a large scale at low temperatures, not much work has been done on the kinetics of mercaptan reaction at such temperatures. Kolthoff, Meehan and Sinha (*J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955 16, 471) determined the chain-transfer constants of primary and tertiary mercaptans in emulsion polymerisation of styrene and butadiene at 5° and found the values slightly higher than the corresponding values at 50°. For low temperature work, they used a redox initiator, as commonly used. Kharash, Nudenberg and Kwahara (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 1550) suggested that at low temperatures, the mercaptan reacted with ferric ions, produced from the redox reaction, and not with the growing polymer radicals, and the resulting mercaptide radical terminated the growing polymer chain instead of reacting with the monomer to start another chain. Thus, the modification by mercaptan at low temperatures proceeds through the mechanism of chain termination instead of chain transfer, which is the accepted mechanism. The object of the present work has been to examine the above suggestion.

As the mechanism of initiation by redox systems, especially the organic hydroperoxides and ferrous salts, is complicated and subject to controversy, it is desirable to use as initiator, the mechanism of which is simple; potassium persulphate is eminently suitable from that consideration. But the thermal decomposition of potassium persulphate at low temperature is so low that it has not been used before. To counteract partially the effect of low temperature, a concentrated solution (almost saturated) of potassium persulphate has been used in the present investigation.

The recipe used (in parts) was styrene 100, water 180, potassium myristate 5, potassium persulphate 3.2, *n*-octylmercaptan 0.5-1.0.

Styrene was first treated with caustic soda solution, washed, dried and distilled twice at 40° under nitrogen atmosphere. Potassium myristate was prepared from myristic acid and crystallised thrice from alcohol and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Potassium persulphate (Merck, G. R) was crystallised from water. *n*-Octylmercaptan (Olin Mathison) was fractionally distilled at low pressure and the fraction at 40-42° was collected; the sulphur content was found as 21.8% against the theoretical value of 21.9%. Experiments were done in Jena bottles with rubber gaskets and nitrogen atmosphere was maintained in the system. Bottles were rotated at 40 r.p.m. inside the bath, kept at a temperature of 5° ± 1°. Samples were withdrawn from the bottle with a hypodermic syringe; for determination of conversion, samples were injected into alcohol containing quinhydrone, wherein the polymer was coagulated; it was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried at 100° and weighed. For mercaptan analysis, samples were injected into

100 c.c. of alcohol containing sufficient ferrous sulphate to decompose persulphate; excess ammonia was added and the mercaptan was amperometrically titrated with standard silver nitrate solution (Kolthoff and Harris, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 161). The chain-transfer constant (C) was calculated with the formula of Mayo,

$$\frac{d \ln(\text{RSH})}{d \ln(M)} = C$$

where RSH designates the mercaptan and M, the monomer.

The rate of polymerisation was found to be 2.1% per hour and it was the same in absence of mercaptan in the above recipe. This is expected from the mechanism of chain transfer. C was found as 19.3; the value found by Kolthoff *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) was 23 with redox initiator. The difference may be due to some reaction of mercaptan with the redox initiator. The thermal decomposition of persulphate is so low that it cannot account for even a very small fraction of disappearance of mercaptan. There is not the slightest doubt about chain-transfer mechanism of mercaptan at 50° with persulphate as initiator; the identical value of the chain-transfer constant with the same initiator at 5° definitely proves the same mechanism of mercaptan at that temperature.

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ON THE PREPARATION OF 4-METHYLCINNOLINE

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The synthesis of 4-methylcinnoline has been described in the literature (Jacobs *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1310; Simpson and Atkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 808). In connection with another work, larger quantities of this substance were required. Attempts to prepare it by the methods already described resulted in small yields. Jacobs' method (*loc. cit.*) of dehydrating the tertiary alcohol (*o*-aminophenyldimethyl carbinol) with iodine in boiling toluene did not prove successful. The preparation of the tertiary alcohol and its subsequent dehydration, however, proceeded smoothly according to the method described by Simpson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The latter authors, however, diazotised and cyclised the crude *o*-isopropenylaniline to 4-methylcinnoline. Attempt to repeat this furnished a deep green residue (as described by Simpson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) but on extracting it with petroleum ether only a red oil was obtained, which could be crystallised with difficulty, affording a small quantity of 4-methylcinnoline. When this oil was distilled under reduced pressure, 4-methylcinnoline was obtained in a low yield (b.p. 146-50°/10 mm).